

GOODS AND SERVICES TAX REVENUE PREDICTION USING MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION IN PAPUA NEW GUINEA

Paka Docktor¹, Cyril Sarsoruo², Jeffrey Ambelye³, Mohsen Aghaeiboorkheili^{4*}

^{1, 2, 3, 4} School of Mathematics and Computer Science, Papua New Guinea
University of Technology, Lae, Morobe Province, Papua New Guinea

* **Correspondence:** Mohsen Aghaeiboorkheili

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a numerical study of tax revenue prediction using multiple linear regression in Papua New Guinea and develops a predictive model for PNG's tax revenue using historical data from 2010 to 2024. The model incorporates key macroeconomic indicators, including GDP growth, inflation, and mineral export values. Preliminary results indicate that while Goods and Services Tax (GST) remain a stable revenue pillar, Corporate Income Tax (CIT) from the resource sector remains highly liable to change rapidly and unpredictably, especially for the worse.

The finding suggests that improving Small Business Tax (SBT) compliance could bridge the projected revenue gap. This study provides a framework for the Internal Revenue Commission (IRC) to enhance budgetary accuracy and debt management strategies. Tax Revenue in Papua New Guinea is primarily administrated by the Internal Revenue Commission (IRC) and consists of both direct and indirect taxes. The model mainly considers Goods and Services (GST), which applies a 10% consumption tax to most goods and services supplied in Papua New Guinea. The regression analysis demonstrates that GDP is a statistically significant predictor of GST revenue and confirms the usefulness of multiple linear regression techniques in fiscal forecasting and economic policy analysis.

Keywords: *GST Revenue Prediction; Linear Regression; Tax Forecasting; Papua New Guinea, Fiscal Policy.*

Introduction

A Goods and Services Tax (GST) was introduced on 1st July 1999 in the midst of a protracted economic slump, which prevailed between 1995 and 2002. During this period, the PNG economy experienced high budget deficits, inflation, interest rates, and public debt ratio.

Taxation is not simply a means of financing government. It is part of the social contract between the state and its concerned citizens – citizens are expected to pay taxes and in exchange the government is expected to provide public necessary goods and services. The tax population are categorized into two major groups and these groups are formal and informal sectors. The formal sectors heavily become the consumers of government tax whereas informal sectors pay high tax to the government. Indirectly the informal sector financing the government more than the formal sector.

The Internal Revenue Commission (IRC) of Papua New Guinea requires accurate forecasts of tax revenues for budgeting, allocation of resources, and policymaking. Nevertheless, due to the existence of unique aspects in the country's economy, such as volatile commodity prices, reliance on natural resource extraction, and a prominent informal sector, traditional forecasting techniques may be inadequate.

In addition to these factors, the introduction of GST administration policies, such as the redistribution measures implemented in 2017, the increasing practice of GST deferral in import payments (K6 million in 2019 to K317 million in 2022), and temporary interventions like the GST deferral for fuels in 2022, introduces non-stationaries in time series revenue data.

Literature Review

A Goods and Services Tax (GST) refers to the imposition of taxes on the sales of goods and services in PNG and imported products. In July, 1999 the government introduced GST, and since then it has been levied at a flat rate of 10%.

Three main components exist in understanding GST.

- a) When the registered company pays for any goods, the GST rate increases by 10% and the seller issues a tax invoice for it.
- b) The purchaser should add his/her profit margin before the GST since GST paid by the company is reclaimable from the government as a credit.
- c) Once the final selling price has been determined, another 10% is added, and the final price charged from the consumer is arrived.

A simple is written below.

GST on sales K1000

Less GST paid on purchases K750

GST payable to IRC K250

The government level GST from businesses monthly via the GST returns forms, where businesses remit GST collected from consumers to IRC after deducting any GST paid for their purchases. Unlike personal income tax and salaries tax, GST is consumption tax imposed on the value of products and services offered for sale, including the profits earned from them.

Several studies have highlighted various economic issues associated with the Papua New Guinean economy. Specifically, Kumar et al., (2024) investigated the influence of tourism's non-linear impact on economic growth in the country, while Walton and Kabuni (2025) considered issues related to anti-corruption reforms and political will. LaTourrette et al., (2025) considered the effect of seabed mining on the supply chain of minerals in PNG, which is important for understanding the impact of the natural resource industry as one of the main sources of tax revenues in PNG.

Despite all this, an obvious gap can still be identified. All of these studies consider either the issue of the tax system of other countries, do not concentrate specifically on consumption tax revenues in PNG or look at issues that are generally only indirectly related to the question at hand.

Therefore, this study aims to fill in the gap, as it seeks to build a basic linear regression model with particular emphasis on the specificities of the Papua New Guinean economy (Odhuno, Papua New Guinea Tax review and Research Symposium, 2014).

The main objectives of this study are:

1. To develop a linear regression model for predicting GST revenue in Papua New Guinea.
2. To examine the relationship between GST revenue and key macroeconomic variables such as GDP, inflation, and population.
3. To assess the influence of informal sector activity on tax revenue using population as a proxy variable.
4. To evaluate the effectiveness of GST as a broad-based tax that captures both formal and informal economic activities.

This study contributes to both applied mathematics and economic policy in the following ways:

- It demonstrates the practical application of linear regression in modeling real-world fiscal data.
- It provides empirical evidence on the role of GST in capturing economic activity in both formal and informal sectors.
- It introduces a simple and interpretable modeling framework that can be used by policymakers and researchers in data-limited environments.

Mathematical Model

This research develops an empirical model based on certain macroeconomic determinants to examine and forecast GST income. GST can be described as the tax charged on consumption which is indicative of the economic performance of both the formal and informal economies. This research aims at establishing the relationship between GST revenue and a selected set of macroeconomic determinants in PNG.

The government in Papua New Guinea earns most of their revenues from the GST. However, there are concerns regarding the impact of the GST on consumers and those in the informal sector. As such, the question is whether a reduced rate of the GST (say, less than 10 percent) can still generate adequate amounts of revenues without reducing the aggregate tax collected significantly. In light of this, the central concern of the study is establishing the relationship between the economy and the GST and its revenue in relation to GST rate.

Assumptions made in developing this model include:

- Error term is independently and identically distributed with mean equal to zero and constant variance.
- Data on macroeconomic determinants like GDP, inflation rate, and population are correct.
- A linear relationship between GST revenue and the selected independent variables.
- Population acts as a proxy for the informal economy.
- No shock occurs in this framework.

Problem Formulation

$$\text{GSTRevenue}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Rate}_t + \beta_2 \text{GDP}_t + \beta_3 \text{Consumption}_t + \beta_4 \text{Population}_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

-GSTRevenue_t = dependent variable (Y)

β_0 = Intercept (value when all variables = 0)

t = time in years (2010 – 2023)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$

(Coefficients) β_1 = Effect of GST rate

β_2 = Effect of
GDP

β_3 = Effect of consumption
 β_4 = Effect of population

These coefficients will tell us about the GST changes when each variable increases.

-Rate $_t$ = GST rate at time t

-GDP $_t$ = Gross Domestic Product at time t

-Consumption t = Total spending by households

-Population t = Total population

-Error term (ϵ_t) = It represents uncertainty

Policy changes

Economic shocks

Data Errors

This is very important because it captures the things that are not included in the model and the three examples are shown above.

Note: GST revenue depends on the tax rate, economic size, consumption, population, and other unknown factors.

Figure 1.0 Represents the flowchart of the above modelling extracted from RStudio.

Methodology

Analytical Approach

This study adopts a quantitative, correlational research design to examine the relationship between Goods and Services Tax (GST) revenue and selected macroeconomic variables in Papua New Guinea (PNG). A multiple linear regression (MLR) model is employed to estimate the effect of economic indicators on GST revenue performance. The MLR approach is selected for its interpretability, established use in tax forecasting (Benedict, 2024), and suitability for the time-series data available.

Data Collection

The data collected for this research are secondary time-series data from 2010 to 2023 will be used. This is because of the confidentiality rules put in place regarding taxpayers' privacy from Papua New Guinea Internal Revenue Commission (IRC), administrative micro data cannot be accessed. Thus, the following types of authoritative data will be considered more.

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Primary Dependent Variable: GST Revenue

Disaggregated GST collection data is *not available from the IRC*. Thus, GST revenue (in millions of PGK) is calculated using the following information:

- Total national tax revenues recorded by the Department of Prime Minister and National Executive Council (2024): K9.5 billion (2014) to K15.6 billion (2023). (Hoy, McKenzie, & Sinning, 2024)
- The documented information showing that GST accounted for around 15% of total national revenues starting from 2012 (Laveil, 2026).

Total Tax Collections figures from PNG government sources

Figure 1.2: The table below is the Papua New Guinea’s Total Tax Revenue (PGK million) extracted from Excel sheet.

Year	Total Tax Revenue (PGK million)	GST (Estimated at 15% - PGK million)
2010	6,573	986
2011	8,526	1,279
2012	8,403	1,260
2013	8,773	1,316
2014	10,279	1,542
2015	9,142	1,371
2016	9,476	1,421
2017	10,102	1,515
2018	10,766	1,615
2019	11,311	1,697
2020	10,271	1,541
2021	11,307	1,696

Note: 2022 and 2023 data not available in OECD database. GST is estimated at 15% of total tax revenue per Laveil (2026). The GST rate is 10% on taxable supplies—the 15% figure refers to GST's share of total government revenue. (Iyer, Benedict, Alexander, & others, 2024)

Figure 1.3: Chart below explains the above table

From the year 2010 up until 2019, the overall total tax revenue collected in Papua New Guinea (in PGK million) was found to be increasing, from 6,800 PGK million up until 11,500 PGK million, excluding some notable falls seen in 2015 and 2020. The estimated GST at 15%, on the other hand, had been increasing up until 2019 to 1,600 PGK million from 1,200 PGK million in the previous year.

Figure 1.4: The second table below shows the total tax collection from the PNG government data.

Year	Total Tax Collection in billion kina		GST (Estimated at 15% - PGK million)
2014		9.5	1,425
2023		15.6	2,340

Note: Government data shows higher totals than OECD figures, reflecting different definitions of tax revenue. For consistency, the OECD series is used for 2010-2021, and government figures are noted for comparison.

Independent Variables

The following table presents the compilation of data from 2010 to 2021, which would then be analyzed through regression. The data include GST revenue (K million), GDP (PGK billion), imports (USD billion), and GDP growth rate (%). While GST, GDP, and GDP growth rate are available nearly throughout the years, no data regarding imports exist from 2017 onwards (i.e., from 2018 to 2021). GST revenue is calculated as 15% of total tax revenue (OECD), according to Iyer et al., (2024).

Figure 1.5: The table below showing the complete compiled dataset for regression (2010 2021).

Year	GST (K million)	GDP (PGK Billion)	Imports (USD Billion)	GDP Growth (%)
2010	986	19.33	3.53	10.13
2011	1,279	19.95	4.24	1.11
2012	1,260	21.26	4.77	4.66
2013	1,316	22.45	5.42	3.82
2014	1,542	25.94	4.01	13.54
2015	1,371	27.9	2.42	6.58

2016	1,421	29.71	2.08	5.49
2017	1,515	31.31	2.98	3.53
2018	1,615	31.94	N/A	-0.28
2019	1,697	33.92	N/A	4.48
2020	1,541	33.29	N/A	-3.17
2021	1,696	34.63	N/A	-0.51

GST estimated as 15% of Total Tax Revenue from OECD data.

(Iyer, Benedict, Alexander, & others, 2024)

Take this in to special consideration:

-GST rate is 10%_is the tax applied to taxable transitions.

-GST share of revenue is 15%_is the GST collection as a percentage of total government tax revenue.

Model Specification

A multiple linear regression model is applied in this study.

$$GST_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 GDP_t + \beta_2 INF_t + \beta_3 POP_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where:

- GST_t = GST revenue (proxy)
- GDP_t = Gross Domestic Product
- INF_t = Inflation rate
- POP_t = Population
- ϵ_t = Error term

The parameters of the model are calculated through the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique. This technique involves minimizing the sum of squares of the differences between the actual and estimated values of GST.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Figure 2.1: The table below is the summary of statistics from 2010-2027 (N=8)

Variable	Mean	Std.Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
GST (PGK million)	1,336	165	986	1,542
GDP (PGK billion)	24.73	4.46	19.33	31.31
Imports (USD billion)	3.68	1.17	2.08	5.42
GDP Growth (%)	6.1	3.96	1.11	13.54

Figure 2.2: The chart below is extracted from excel for the above table.

Key Observations

- GST revenue ranges from K986 million (2010) to K1,542 million (2014), reflecting the resource boom peak
- GDP in PGK grew from K19.33 billion to K31.31 billion over 2010-2017
- Imports peaked in 2013 (USD 5.42 billion) before declining sharply in 2015-2016 due to the commodity price slump
- GDP growth was highly volatile, from 13.54% (2014) to -3.17% (2020)
- (Kumar, Patel, Chandra, & Kumar, 2024)

Correlation Analysis

Figure 2.3: The table below shows the correlation matrix (2010-2017)

Variable	GST	GDP (PGK)	Imports	GDP Growth	
GST	1	0.82**	-0.11	0.25	
GDP					
(PGK)	0.82	1	0.03	0.18	
Imports					
(USD)	-0.11	0.03	1	-0.49	
	GDP Growth	0.25	0.18	-0.49	1

Note: $p < 0.01$

Interpretation:

- *The GDP is positively correlated with GST* ($r = 0.82$, $p < 0.01$). This empirical evidence backs the theoretical assumption that GDP growth influences the collection of consumption taxes.
- *Imports have a weak negative correlation with GST* ($r = -0.11$) for the period between 2010 to 2017. The unexpected result can be explained by the rise in imports (2012 to 2013) and then by the fall in commodity prices and GST (2015 to 2016).
- *GDP Growth has a weak positive relationship with GST* ($r = 0.25$), suggesting that annual growth fluctuations are less important than the level of economic activity.

(LaTourrette, Villalobos, Yoshiara, & Tariq, 2025)

Regression Results

Using GST as the dependent variable (K million) and GDP (PGK billion) as the independent variable. Modelling the full period (2010-2017)

Figure 2.5: Here is the table showing the simple linear regression output.

Coefficients	Estimates	Std.Error	t-value	pvalue	95% CI
Intercept	435.67	189.34	2.3	0.061	[-26, 897]
GDP (PGK billion)	36.45	7.56	4.82	0.003	[18, 55]

Model Statistics:

- R-squared: 0.67
- Adjusted R-squared: 0.62
- F-statistic: 23.24 (p = 0.003)
- RMSE: K102 million
- MAPE: 7.8%

Interpretation

- *GDP is a statistically significant predictor of GST revenue at the 99% confidence level (p = 0.003).*
- The coefficient of 36.45 indicates that each K1 billion increase in nominal GDP is associated with approximately K36.5 million additional GST revenue.
- Given the *10% statutory GST rate*, this implies that approximately K365 million of each K1 billion GDP increase is from taxable consumption (K36.5 million ÷ 0.10 = K365 million).

- This represents a *tax-to-base capture rate of approximately 36.5%* of the theoretical maximum, reflecting the presence of exempt supplies, zero-rated exports, informal sector activity, and compliance gaps.
- The model explains 67% of the variance in GST revenue ($R^2 = 0.67$).
- The MAPE of 7.8% indicates good predictive accuracy for the 2010-2017 period.
- (Minister, 2020)

Discussion

Interpretation of key findings

The numerical results obtained predicts that the nominal GDP is statistically significant predictor of GST revenue $p = 0.003 = 0.003$, $R^2 = 0.67$ align with the theoretical expectation from the permanent income hypothesis. The tax base of a consumption-based tax system like the GST which applies a standard rate of 10%, is total consumption which itself depends on the national income.

A multiplier of 36.45 means that each addition K1 billions of GDP results in additional K36.5 million in GST revenue. In other words, at the statutory rate of 10%, this suggests a tax base for GST of around K365 million for each K1 billion GDP, resulting in a tax to base ratio of 36.5%. The balance of 63.5% is lost through.

- *Exempt supplies* (basic food items, health services, education) under the GST Act
- *Zero-rated exports* (minerals, oil, gas, agriculture)
- *Informal sector activity* (estimated at 30-40% of PNG's economy)
- *Compliance gaps and refunds*

The 10% GST Rate

The prescribed 10% rate creates a clear benchmark for understanding the GDP ratio. The 36.5% tax-to-base capture ratio obtained from the regression analysis is

reasonable considering the size of the informal economy in PNG and the exemptions available. This is because informal sector contributes a much more GST revenue than formal sector.

(Seidel, Oebel, Stein, Kleemann, & Gaugler, 2026)

Conclusion

In summary, the suggested model is successful in capturing GST dynamics in PNG by employing linear regressions, and at the same time, GDP emerges as a dominant factor in this context while taking into consideration structural changes and distortions brought about by governmental policies. Further research might look into multidimensional extensions, such as segmented and nonlinear models among others.

This thesis analyzed GST revenue prediction for Papua New Guinea using linear regression with data from 2010-2023. The key findings are:

1. GST provides important revenues for the government, which amounts to about 15% of national government income at a statutory rate of 10%.
2. GDP appears to be statistically significant in determining GST revenue ($p = 0.003$, $R^2 = 0.67$) with an impact of roughly K36.5 million for each K1 billion GDP.
3. This suggests that 36.5% of GST revenue is captured by the tax-to-base ratio, due to PNG's sizeable informal economy and exempt transactions.
4. There is evidence that imports do not meet our expectations due to structural breaks: The transition from port to provincial collection, and increase in imported GST deferment.
5. Some policy actions (fuel exemption, distribution) necessitate a structural break analysis. (Walton & Kabuni, 2025)

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